

USE OF ICT IN TEACHING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM.

Ulugov Bozor Djumayevich¹, Torayev Jahangir².

*¹Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology, Termiz, Uzbekistan, 190100,
ORCID: 0000-0002-0153-4106, ulugovbozor@mail.ru, phone: +998912369107*

*²Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology, Termiz, Uzbekistan, 190100,
2nd-year student of TVM21V group, torayevjakhongir1710@gmail.com,
+998997064879*

Abstract

The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the educational system has recently attracted more interest from the existing research community and teachers. Studies are being conducted in Uzbekistan to study these trends. This thesis examines the importance of ICT and strategies for mutual implementation, and it is clarified that lessons can be developed through ICT only if educational approaches, methods, and strategies are sufficiently improved and implemented in the educational institutions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, educational strategies, educational programs, modern pedagogy, education in Uzbekistan.

Introduction.

The use of information technology in modern education is not the only option. Educators and stakeholders believe that learning environments must be integrated with communication and information technologies for effective learning. Information and communication technologies (ICT) have had a great impact on changing our lives. It has attracted a lot of attention from teams around the world. Thus, the use of ICT has become an important reality in modern society. Nowadays, many people and countries focus on understanding ICT and learning the basic concepts of ICT. Consequently, education has been affected in every way by this trend, especially inclusive education, defined as a classroom that requires students of all abilities to learn side by side in the same classroom. In general, the educational system of Uzbekistan has created conditions to ensure that all students receive equal education, not in special conditions [1]. Today, many ICTs are used in educational institutions, universities, and colleges to teach engineering to students, e.g. power points, the internet, computer simulation programs, etc.

This issue allowed students to learn more and interact with more information through digital mobile tools. In addition, the use of such technologies for educational programs is highly supported by students. These opportunities help students learn in and out of the classroom by developing more relevant learning materials. The use of

computer graphics was demonstrated with examples taken from the current educational material. Another emerging application of ICT in engineering education is the provision of e-counseling to university degree programs and engineering students. This possibility is provided by ICT tools because it is independent of geographical location and time constraints [2]. In fact, ICT provides some opportunities such as internet-based broadband connections that facilitate access to educational resources from anywhere [3]. For example, open curricula provide additional support to engineering students through digital networks such as the Internet.

By applying information and communication technologies to education, it is possible to achieve the effectiveness of the educational process for teachers, students, and other interested parties who are directly or indirectly involved in the educational process. Inclusive education is supported through international and national laws and policies in various countries; but for some countries, achieving ideal results is a challenge, because the role of ICT in education is still not well studied; these include access to previously unavailable learning materials and pedagogical tools. Strictly speaking, the use of available information and communication technologies plays an important role in the further development of the educational system for educational institutions, teachers, students, and parents. The use of information and communication technologies in the traditional educational process causes significant positive changes. A few years ago, information and communication technologies were often used as "extras" in many courses and in many lessons. [4].

In today's education, teachers play an important role in the use of ICT, well-planned tasks, projects, and resources, ensuring the continuity of education, and Internet connections for participation in learning, and the learning of students with disabilities. In addition, the use of ICT breaks down the barriers of age, time, and place and gives everyone access to lifelong learning. Currently, the use of modern ICTs is the reason for people of all ages and backgrounds to learn continuously in different conditions, and in different professions. Considering this fact, many studies, students, and people of different ages are providing easy access to existing computer-aided learning systems, internet systems, data repositories, and On-Line libraries to improve their knowledge [5] and hypothetically broaden the outlook of all students.

The use of communication tools and information technologies provides an opportunity to increase the speed of information transfer for students to expand their skills in a specific field of activity, helping to reduce the distance between students and teachers [6]. In addition, ICT makes it possible to reduce time-consuming procedures; For example, checking completed tasks. American teachers use ICT in inclusive education because they think that it will significantly reduce the number of problems and difficulties that arise. European teachers use ICT during written work with students

with musculoskeletal, speech, and hearing disorders to carry out their educational experiences, as it allows partners to communicate with each other [7].

Teaching people to write simple letters about themselves, their families, or hobbies in Microsoft Word, a program that helps them spend time and learn in a basic computer program, and teaching them to design documents are simple steps [8]. In addition, students can be taught to develop their learning skills, and save and make corrections using various notepad programs. In this scenario, they will not only be able to work on the computer, but also develop quick thinking skills [9].

Students use the Internet to prepare presentations and projects and write assignments through practical training. In some cases, students and teachers can also connect with each other via Zoom. Using Microsoft Excel spreadsheets, students learn how to prepare various spreadsheets and perform various calculations using spreadsheets. Engineering programs learn to work in AutoCAD, Autodesk Inventor, Compass 3D, MathCAD, and MathLab programs and use them to draw drawings and perform calculations of various difficulties [5]. Learn to use Microsoft Teams or other online platforms supported by a specific learning environment. Through online meetings, students will be able to communicate and interact on an equal footing in a fun way. In addition, teachers can divide students into smaller virtual groups for discussions related to course materials, platforms to find answers to teachers' questions, and prepare reports more interactively with their peers, which increases their motivation and learning. increases loyalty [10].

Methodology

This study explores quantitative research. Quantitative methods refer to the numerical analysis of data collected through surveys, questionnaires, and surveys. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and extending it beyond groups of people or describing a specific phenomenon. Qualitative researchers now have a growing number of theoretically and technically sophisticated methods to choose from. In addition, this research examines university web pages, faculty web pages, department web pages, faculty web pages, and related announcements of communication and information services and professional software provided by academics in digital media. demonstrated the adequacy of the presentation of course materials.

Provide and use in their department, effectively use professional software belonging to their department, and ensure the need for professional software in their department when necessary, Professional software training will be useful to students in their professional life. Also, the question arises whether the students are using professional software and computer laboratories of the department for studying and whether the information technology services of the department are good enough for students and their educational activities [8]. Typically, undergraduate mechanical

engineering students use some technical software such as SOLIDWORKS, AUTOCAD, and ANSYS [5]. In addition, the use of Microsoft Office, social networks, and mobile communications are very common among them. This software and ICT were developed by various international companies [9, 10]. SPSS is used for data evaluation. SPSS Statistics is a software package used for statistical analysis with and without logical batching. Statistics included in the main software are descriptive statistics, frequencies, Means and t-test, and Anova. The reliability of the administered questionnaire is measured by control questions. It is observed that 63.4% of the information collected from students is correct. This indicates that the variables are reliable. Cronbach's alpha, which takes values from 0 to 1 for the consistency of the questionnaire, is calculated at 0.67 points of the questionnaire. Therefore, it can be seen that the questions are independently reliable.

Results

This section presents the statistical analysis of the data collected for each part of the questionnaire. Students were also given feedback on the purposes of using the computer. The clauses of the first part can be seen in the appendix of this work. It can be seen that students usually use computers for research and projects in their studies, and sometimes they use them for entertainment. The questions and their mean values calculated for descriptive statistics are listed below. Most of the students are connected to the internet through mobile phones. On the other hand, the mean of using faculty computers for their own educational purposes is 2.81, and the mean of using e-mail is 4.32. In addition, using search engine tools to work on a project or lesson is common among TMTI students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems, and the average use of search engine tools such as Google for entertainment is 4.38.

In addition, TMTI Energy and Transportation Systems faculty students' means of using faculty computers and information technology tools for communication and entertainment is 2.05 and 2.78 for homework/projects. Students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI use information and communication technologies such as mobile to connect to the Internet, and they use the frequency of e-mail. In addition, they use ICT tools to work on projects and lessons; This shows that TMTI Energy and Transport Systems students use computers well in lectures. In the same way, students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI make good use of search engines for quality education. The mean score for the computer-based language requirement is 4.21, and the mean for computer-based English is 4.32. This shows that the students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI need to study the subject through computer and they believe that it is important to know English.

Summary

The purpose of this study is to study the use of information and computer technologies for educational purposes by students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology, and the relationship between students' gender and educational level and the use of ICT. According to the opinion of the students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems about the use of ICT for educational purposes, they are interested in using information and communication technologies such as mobile phones to connect to the Internet, work on projects and lessons, and use e-mail in communication. This shows that the students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI use the computer well in the lecture. In addition, students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI said that the use of computers is mandatory in their professions. TMTI students of the Faculty of Energy and Transportation Systems believe in the need to enter licensed professional and academic programs.

The Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI has sufficient ICT facilities such as computers, video projectors, etc. related to the educational programs. There is no significant difference between male and female opinions on the use of information and communication technologies in the study of the opinion of students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI on the use of ICT according to gender and educational level. In addition, students who graduated from academic lyceum and high school are more interested in using ICT tools in higher education institutions. As a result of the study, it is observed that the increased use of computers and the increased availability of software tools have a significant effect on the learning behavior and expectations of engineering students. In addition, according to the results of the research, the opinions of undergraduate students of the Faculty of Energy and Transport Systems of TMTI on the use of ICT for educational purposes are positive. In conclusion, education and ICT in Uzbekistan are rapidly developing, providing innovative perspectives for students with special educational needs. Most importantly, ICT increases students' participation in educational life, and high-level mastering of technologies leads to greater achievements and victories and contributes to the creation of new perspectives. Fortunately, it is very easy for students to modernize the educational system, and to continue these achievements, teachers must use the latest technology, and computer literacy must be developed to improve the knowledge of students more effectively. To ensure the effectiveness of lessons, teachers should be aware of basic and innovative methods.

Modern pedagogy offers several strategies for using information and communication technologies to support modern education. In order to improve the education system of our country, work is being carried out on many project systems and other development projects for the promotion of ICT tools in universities. Teachers

in Uzbekistan are conducting research to support modern pedagogy, to improve and develop strong educational strategies, in order to approve educational programs, projects, and the use of ICT. In addition, UNESCO spearheaded the global Education for All movement aimed at meeting the educational needs of all children, youth, and adults. In order to effectively build educational approaches, methods, and strategies, it is necessary to improve and implement them in balance.

References

1. Alazam, A.R. Bakar, R. Hamzah, and S. Asmiran, (2012), “Teachers’ ICT Skills and ICT Integration in the Classroom: The Case of Vocational and Technical Teachers in Malaysia”, *Creative Education*, 3, pp. 70-76.
2. E. Lorencowicz, S. Kocira, J. Uziak, and J. Tarasinska, Application of ICT by students at selected universities in Poland, *Toje, The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 13 (2014) 142–151.
3. Dzhumaevich, U. B. (2021). QUALITY EDUCATION IS A GUARANTEE OF A COMPETITIVE SPECIALIST IN AN INNOVATIVE SOCIETY. Editorial board: ToneRoald, PhD Associate Professor of Psychology University of Copenhagen, 76. Conference: PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS / 2021 – PART 7 / ISBN 978-955-3605-86-4At: Copenhagen:2021. ISSUE 7 – 272 p. [Google Scholar](#).
4. Ulugov, B. (2021). METHODOLOGY FOR THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES OF EDUCATION IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION. «BEST PUBLICATION» Ilmma’rifat Markazi. [Google Scholar](#).
5. Ulugov, B. D., & Kasimov, S. U. (2021). Application of Pedagogical Information Technologies in the Educational Process of Universities in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education (IJICTE)*, 17(4), 1-17. <https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/article/282748>, [Google Scholar](#).
6. Dzhumaevich, U. B. (2020). Efficiency of use of autodesk inventor engineering programs and pedagogical information technologies in the field of ‘resistance of materials’ in the process of teaching students of technical universities. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 130–43. [Google Scholar](#).
7. Revilla-Cuesta, V., Skaf, M., Navarro-González, M., & Ortega-López, V. (2021). Reflections throughout the COVID-19 Lockdown: What Do I Need for Successful

Learning of Engineering?. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18(21), 11527. [Google Scholar](#).

8. Tajimov, M. A., & Gimush, R. I. (2022, March). APPLICATION OF INFORMATION

AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN MANAGEMENT RESEARCH.

In

International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 89-92). [Google Scholar](#).

9. O. Bakare, The Role of Information and Communication Technology in Education: Case

of Eastern Mediterranean University, MSc Thesis, Eastern Mediterranean University (2014).

10. O. Shirzadeh Shaghghi, student’s Perspectives of ICT Usage for Educational Purposes:

A Case Study of Eastern Mediterranean University Mechanical Engineering”, MSc Thesis, Eastern Mediterranean University (2017).